

Inclusive self-ascription in teachers of the Province of Tambopata, Peru: A comparative study

Autoadscripción inclusiva en docentes de la Provincia de Tambopata, Perú: Un estudio comparativo

Jimmy N. Paricahua Peralta*, Doctor en Educación, Universidad Nacional Amazónica de Madre de Dios, Perú. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9399-5956>. E-mail: jparicahua@unamad.edu.pe

Yeni Gutierrez Acuña, Doctora en Medio Ambiente y Desarrollo Sostenible, Universidad Andina del Cusco, Perú. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3836-3398> E-mail: ygutierrez@uandina.edu.pe

Juan C. Valencia Martinez, Doctor en Ciencias de la Salud, Universidad Andina del Cusco, Perú. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6024-3392> E-mail: jvalenciam@uandina.edu.pe

Edwin G. Estrada Araoz, Doctor en Educación, Universidad Nacional Amazónica de Madre de Dios, Perú. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4159-934X>. E-mail: edwin5721@outlook.com

Percy A. Zevallos Pollito, Doctor en Ciencias, Universidad Nacional Amazónica de Madre de Dios, Perú. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4961-791X>. E-mail: pazpolli@unamad.edu.pe

Libertad Velásquez Giersch, Magíster en Gestión Pública, Universidad Andina del Cusco, Perú. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8608-269X>. E-mail: lvelasquezg@uandina.edu.pe

Luis Urbina Puma, Magíster en Ciencias de la Educación, Universidad Nacional Amazónica de Madre de Dios, Perú. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0021-3474>. E-mail: lurbina@unamad.edu.pe

Llen A. Meza Orue, Magíster en Gestión Pública, Universidad Nacional Amazónica de Madre de Dios, Perú. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4749-8224>. E-mail: lmeza@unamad.edu.pe

*Jimmy N. Paricahua Peralta. E-mail: jparicahua@unamad.edu.pe

The authors declare that the research was self-financed and we have no conflict of interest.

Received: 06/26/2021 Accepted: 09/15/2022 Published: 09/25/2022 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7479893>

660

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to compare the predisposition toward inclusive self-ascription in teachers of the initial level educational institutions of the initial level of the Province of Tambopata. Teachers, assistants, and directors of educational institutions in the urban and rural areas of the Province of Tambopata were considered part of the population. For the collection of information, the Inclusion Index was used, an instrument with adequate psychometric properties composed of 44 items. It was concluded that, in the Province of Tambopata, the predisposition towards inclusive self-ascription was significantly the same in teachers from urban and rural educational institutions at the initial level. This would imply that the teachers who work, both in the urban and rural geographical areas, would have a similar perception regarding the opportunities and weaknesses that exist in relation to culture, practice, and inclusive policies.

Keywords: Education, inclusive culture, inclusive practices, inclusive policies.

Resumen

El estudio tuvo la finalidad de comparar la predisposición hacia la autoadscripción inclusiva en docentes del nivel de inicial de las instituciones educativas del nivel de inicial de la Provincia de Tambopata. Se consideró como parte de la población a docentes, auxiliares y directivos de instituciones educativas del ámbito urbano y rural de la Provincia de Tambopata. Para la recolección de la información se hizo uso del Índice de Inclusión, instrumento con adecuadas propiedades psicométricas compuesto por 44 ítems. Se concluyó que, en la Provincia de Tambopata, la predisposición hacia la autoadscripción inclusiva era significativamente igual en docentes de instituciones educativas urbanas y rurales del nivel inicial. Esto implicaría que los docentes que laboran, tanto en la zona geográfica urbana o rural, tendrían similar percepción en cuanto a las oportunidades y debilidades que se dan en relación con la cultura, la práctica y las políticas inclusivas.

Palabras clave: Educación, cultura inclusiva, prácticas inclusivas, políticas inclusivas.

Education in Peru is facing and will face a challenge related to the inclusion of children in regular basic educational institutions; therefore, all institutions nationwide must reserve at least two vacancies per classroom, for students with mild or moderate disabilities¹. This educational policy determines that teachers at different levels must adapt their educational practice to work and attention, considering that learning, as well as the development of human beings, is heterogeneous and not homogeneous, and there is a need for an approach committed to diversity. However, as indicated by Chipana², awareness of inclusion is decisive because it must allow teachers to be oriented to understand differences, internalize them, and predispose their educational practice aimed at achieving the improvement of students not only with different abilities but in general, favoring attitudinal barriers to be broken and students can have a participatory training³. Therefore, a student who does not share favorable educational experiences, such as sensory, interaction, and attention, among others, could further complicate or affect their development and adaptation to society.

As Fernández⁴ warns, difficulties become disabilities when the environment and interaction do not have the necessary support to care for people. Therefore, teaching must be aimed at promoting tolerance, capacity building, and understanding, contributing to inclusion to reduce inequalities⁵. However, as evidenced by Rubio and Martínez⁶, there would be members of the community, families, and even teachers indifferent to problems related to disability, showing a disinterested attitude for not being able to understand the differences, related in part. This problem could be related in part to their training based on an educational approach of competition with others, coexistence in the family environment, the agents that were decisive in their socialization process, the limited approach, and the relationship with people with different abilities⁷.

It is necessary to highlight how decisive participation is in the structuring and planning to accommodate differences, by teachers, there would be other factors related to the establishment of an inclusive culture such as training and teaching practice as a purpose that must be corrected short term⁸. However, it is necessary to clarify as indicated Barbera⁹, that exclusion would affect every individual affected by marginalization and isolation, therefore, the school is an agent of inclusion, but it must go beyond the curriculum, methodology or didactics, specifically to promote participation, communication, and interaction in the community social context.

Disability is a reality that characterizes a part of the population of people in the world; there are possibilities of humans being born with one or several disabilities or throughout life, they could appear; as in aging, the chances of acquiring some disabilities increase¹⁰. The concept of disability homogenizes various types of physical, sensory, social, cultural, and urban limitations or all of them¹¹. It is a way of manifesting the human condition because it helps to examine constitutive aspects of existence such as our changing over time or being dependent and vulnerable¹².

There are two historical edges, regarding the person with disabilities, the first implies the rejection of the society that was sentenced to death or exile; this situation lasted for many years; in the next one the disabled are accepted, they are accepted and treated humanely, which was understood and understood better, with the appearance of Christianity¹⁰. However, a third edge could be considered, which is based on the idea that disability is more than anything a social fact, derived from the very design of society for people without disabilities, as the majority. This model is given by a society that is not prepared or designed to meet the needs¹¹.

The construction of environments that favor the self-determination of subjects with disabilities, as well as the awareness of these actors about the potential development of their capacities, their life project, and their capacity for individual and collective political action. Thus, this composite operation involves family, friends, support networks, and society in general, without whom the subject of disability would not be in a position to enhance their abilities¹². The loss of qualities with a disability, although it represents an important change for the individual, does not imply a decrease or exclusion of the human condition, much less of the personal condition, even in cases where there is loss or no manifestation of rationality¹³.

The problem of the research was centralized in understanding the predisposition of teachers in the urban-rural environment towards inclusive self-ascription. Figure 1 shows the organization that disposition to inclusion that teachers have. Likewise, this would be established in three pillars proposed by Booth y Ainscow¹⁵, three being raised: culture, practices, and inclusive policies. The first refers to the organization and support modalities to address diversity; the second, to teaching learning and the development of inclusive values; and the last, to the actions and possibilities of change within the educational field.

Figure 1. Pillars of inclusive self-ascription^{14,15}

It must be noted that the pandemic caused by coronavirus had an opposite effect on education due to the suspension of face-to-face classes, with asynchronous, synchronous, and remote education being the main channel of communication between teachers and children in initial education who were the main affected because they would not have had adequate stimulation when entering the initial educational institution and allow an adequate process of articulation to primary education to be carried out. Likewise, this reality could have affected, exacerbated, and increased the inclusion of children with different abilities in relation to learning or neurodevelopmental problems.

Thus, the objective of this research was to compare the predisposition toward inclusive self-ascription in teachers at the initial level of educational institutions at the initial level of the Province of Tambopata.

Materials and methods

The study corresponds to the type of basic research because its purpose is to increase and deepen information regarding the level of belonging, commitment, and attitudes of teachers towards inclusion. The type of research was descriptive since it sought to analyze the inclusive self-ascription variable without manipulating it through an independent variable, likewise, it is compared because the samples of the educational institutions were contrasted. The research design corresponds to the cross-sectional model because the data collection was carried out in a single time cut and not longitudinally.

Directors, teachers, and education assistants from educational institutions at the initial level of the urban and rural geographic area of the Province of Tambopata, which includes 4 districts: Inambari, Las Piedras, Laberinto, and Tambopata, were considered study participants. The type of sample was used for convenience, due to accessibility, proximity to the interoceanic highway, and other means that were not wild. In the first place, the population of the urban area was comprised of 231 participants with a sample distribution of 145, divided into 117 representatives of the district of Tambopata who made up 80.5%; 11 from the district of Inambari, making up 7.8%; 9 to the district of Las Piedras, representing 6.1% and 8 to the district of Laberinto, meaning 5.6%. Second, the population of the rural area was 75 participants, with a sample distribution of 63, divided into 11 representatives from the district of Tambopata, making up 17.3%, 36 from the district of Inambari, meaning 57.3%, and finally, 16 of the districts of Las Piedras corresponding to 25.3%.

For the collection of information, the Teacher Inclusion Index Questionnaire¹⁵ was used, composed of 44 items, and structured in 3 dimensions: the first measures the inclusive culture of teachers and is made up of items 1 to 14; the second dimension evaluates inclusive policies and is evaluated with items 15 to 33; Finally, the third, the inclusive practical dimension, is measured with items 34 to 45. The scale and indexes for the tabulation of the database are: completely agree (3), agree (2), disagree (1), and strongly disagree (0).

For the analysis of the information, first, descriptive statistics were used to identify the levels in which the participants of the sample were located to make a comparison between the districts that have teachers in the urban geographic area and rural. To test the research hypothesis, the assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity were checked to meet the requirements for applying the Student's t-test for independent samples.

Results

Figure 2 shows the percentage distribution of the level of inclusive self-ascription (AI) in the four districts of the urban area of the province of Tambopata, in which the level of high predisposition stands out, the district of Inambari (ID) the one with the highest percentage with 81.8%, followed by the district of Tambopata (TD) with 50.4%; in third place is the district of Laberinto (LD) with 50%; while, in the latter, with 44.4%, the district of Las Piedras (LPD) would be positioned. Next, (LPD) and (TD) would be the only two that present a very low predisposition, being the largest (LPD) with 11.1% and the second (TD) with 0.9%. On the other hand, (LPD), (LD), and (TD) would be the districts that have a median predisposition, the first with 44.4%, the second with 37.5%, and the third with 31.6%. On the other hand, the district of the urban geographic zone that is located in the first place between the high and very high levels, corresponded to Inambari representing 100%, in second place, the district of Tambopata was located with 65.8% corresponding to both. Levels, in third place, was the district of Labyrinth with 62.5%; in the last place was the district of Las Piedras with 44%, only with the level of high predisposition. Finally, the districts of Laberinto and Inambari did not have participants located in the low and very low levels, however, Tambopata and Las Piedras obtained percentages in the level of very low predisposition.

Figure 2. Level of inclusive self-ascription in the urban geographic area of the province of Tambopata

Figure 3 shows that the predominant level in the districts of rural areas of the province of Tambopata was that of high predisposition, the first place with 58.3% was obtained by Inambari (ID), followed by Tambopata (TD) with 45.5%, and in third place was located Las Piedras (LPD) 43.8%. In the level of very high and high predisposition (ID), it was in the first place with 69.4%, in second place, it was (TD) with 63.7% while the last place was occupied by (LPD) with 62.3%. It must be noted that the three districts obtained scores at the level of medium predisposition, however, no district had scored at the levels of low and very low predisposition.

Figure 3. Level of inclusive self-ascription in the rural geographical area of the province of Tambopata

Table 1 specifies the application of the two tests required to use the t-test for independent samples. First, to meet the assumption of Normality, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was applied; the score obtained for the urban geographic area was 0.070; while the rural geographic area received 0.20. Proving that both groups came from populations with approximately normal distribution. Second, to comply with the homoscedasticity assumption, the Levene test was applied, obtaining the calculated significance of 0.453, which turned out to be greater than 0.50 and it was shown that the sample data come from populations with similar or equal variances. Both cases were shown to meet the assumptions for the use of the Student's t-test.

Table 1. Assumptions required for the application of the Student's t-test.

Normality			Homoscedasticity	
Kolmogorov-Smirnov test			Levene's test	
Variable	Geographic area	Sig.	F	Sig.
Inclusive self-ascription	Urban	0.070	0.565	0.453
	Rural	0.200		

Table 2 shows the results obtained from the application of the Student's t-test for independent samples. Obtaining a significance of 0.919 >0.05 for the urban geographic area and 0.914 >0.05 for the rural geographic area. Therefore, the research hypothesis is accepted: In the educational institutions

of the province of Tambopata, the predisposition towards self-ascription inclusive is significantly the same in teachers of urban and rural educational institutions of the initial level.

Table 2. Student's t-test for hypothesis testing of independent samples

Variable	Geographic area	Mean	Standard deviation	gl.	t	Sig.	d	1-β
Inclusive self-ascription	Urban	88.92	19.254	206	-0.102	0.919	0.02	0.06
	Rural	89.21	16.212	139	-0.109	0.914		

Discussion

The findings presented in Figures 2 and 3, showed that both in the urban and rural geographical areas, the level of high predisposition towards inclusive self-ascription prevailed in teachers, being higher in the urban area 56.7% than in the rural area at 48.2% according to the average of the percentage sums. These data are similar to the reported by Ortega¹⁶, whose results revealed that 75% of the sample of teachers was located in the acceptable parameter regarding the inclusion index. Likewise, Nasqui et al.¹⁷, found that teachers have a favorable attitude, however, they cannot adequately fulfill the task of inclusion and make the inclusion process favorable. In the same way, Arias¹⁸ found that a part of the teachers presented a favorable attitude towards people with disabilities, and another with an indecisive attitude towards the acceptance of people with disabilities. Secondly, Suárez¹⁹, determined in its results that 51.2% evidence of the existence of good practice of inclusive education, followed by 46.8% with regular practice, and finally only 2% with bad practice.

Secondly, the data obtained in Figures 2 and 3, reflected that the teachers of the urban and rural geographical areas were also located at the level of medium predisposition towards inclusive self-ascription, which can be represented as indecision of the teachers in the psychic disposition against situations of diversity and inclusion. These results are corroborated by the conclusion of Toapanta²⁰ which indicated that the teaching attitude towards inclusion is limited because diversity and interest in the progress of students in the learning process are not fully considered. Similarly, it is related to the results of Muñoz et al.²¹, who indicated an attitude of indecision towards attention to diversity, pointing out as a limitation the limited socialization of public inclusion policies that allow attention to the diversity of students. In addition, Yanac²² determined in his research that teachers had an attitude of indecision towards educational inclusion, mainly due to the cognitive component, that is, they consider that they are insufficiently trained to assume this task, being different in each educational center. These results reflect that teachers would have limited training in terms of inclusive education practice because they would be unaware of the forms of work to provide educational care to this population²³.

Finally, the verification of the research hypothesis represented in Table 2, would show that in the educational institutions of the province of Tambopata, the predisposition towards inclusive self-ascription is significantly the same in teachers

of urban and rural educational institutions of the initial level. It could be considered that inclusion is a process that does not imply a radical change from one moment to another, but rather, of a reasonable time and period, so it must be planned, programmed, followed up, and given feedback according to the case of progress²⁴. These limitations could be explained due to the large number of students who must be served in classrooms that exceed the limit for a single teacher, apart from attending positions related to administrative issues, which makes it difficult to provide adequate attention to students²⁵. Likewise, educational practices would not be enough to address the learning difficulties of students, so the use of traditional teaching techniques that do not respond to the special needs of children with disabilities has resorted to²⁶. Therefore, the inclusive process in educational institutions would be determined by factors that affect positively, as well as negatively, being two the most representative: the first would be self-efficacy, while the second would be related to the initial and continuous training that the teachers develop²⁷.

Conclusions

According to the t-test for equality of means, the calculated significance was greater than 0.05, so it can be affirmed that in the Province of Tambopata the predisposition towards inclusive self-ascription is significantly equal in teachers of urban and rural educational institutions of the educational initial level. This would imply that teachers who work both in the urban and rural geographic areas would have a similar perception regarding the opportunities and weaknesses that exist in relation to an inclusive culture, practice, and policies.

References

1. Ministerio de Educación. Colegios deben reservar dos vacantes por aula para estudiantes con discapacidad. Lima: MINEDU; 2019.
2. Chipana, M. Intervención de los docentes en el proceso de adaptación del niño con necesidades educativas especiales a un aula regular de Educación Inicial en cuatro Instituciones del distrito de Cercado de Lima. Lima: Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú; 2016.
3. Mantilla, N. Inclusión educativa para niños y niñas de edad preescolar con capacidades especiales diferentes. Ecuador: Universidad Andina Simón Bolívar; 2019.
4. Fernández, C. Capacidades diversas y educación social. Madrid: Ediciones Pirámide; 2019.
5. Ramírez, W. La inclusión: una historia de exclusión en el proceso de enseñanza-aprendizaje. Cuadernos de Lingüística Hispánica. 2017. (30):211-230. <https://doi.org/10.19053/0121053X.n30.0.6195>
6. Rubio, L., & Martínez, M. Representaciones sociales de docentes y padres de familia sobre inclusión educativa de niños con discapacidad cognitiva en la institución educativa Técnico Industrial de Turmequé. Colombia: Universidad Santo Tomás; 2019.
7. Peraza, B. Evaluación de la gestión en el área académica del programa de inclusión escolar en el colegio Inem Santiago Pérez, sección primaria, jornada tarde. Colombia: Universidad Externado de Colombia; 2019.
8. Campa, R. Proceso de inclusión educativa para la atención a la diversidad: Propuestas de mejora en la Educación Primaria del Estado de Sonora. Sonora: Universidad de Sonora; 2017.
9. Barbera, M. La inclusión de niños con necesidades educativas especiales en la escuela primaria en relación con el contexto socio-cultural y la personalidad del grupo de clase. Almería: Universidad de Almería; 2018.
10. Diaz, J. Discapacidad en el Perú: Un análisis de la realidad a partir de datos estadísticos. Revista Venezolana de Gerencia. 2019. 24(85):243-263. <https://produccioncientificaluz.org/index.php/rvg/article/view/23838>
11. Cruz, B. El mundo y los mundos de la discapacidad. Cuicuilco. Revista de Ciencias Antropológicas. 2019. 26(75):117-147. <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=529562356007>
12. Alcántara, N., & Ornelas, G. La interculturalidad y la discapacidad en entornos universitarios. REencuentro. Análisis de Problemas Universitarios. 2018. 29(75):133-154. <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=34060766007>
13. Enríquez, Y. Discapacidad: una heurística para la condición humana. Revista Bioética. 2018. 26(2):207-216. <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=361558416007>
14. Castro, F., Castañeda, M., Ossa, C., Blanco, E., & Castillo, H. Validación de la escala de autoadscripción inclusiva en docentes secundarios de Chile. Psicología Educativa. 2017. 23:105-113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pse.2017.05.003>
15. Booth, T., & Ainscow, M. Índice de inclusión, Desarrollando el aprendizaje y la participación en las escuelas. Reino Unido: UNESCO; 2002.
16. Ortega, M. Correlación entre la inclusión y el Simce: (Caso: Escuelas municipales Comuna en Chile). Revista Científica. 2019. 4:18-37. <https://doi.org/10.29394/Scientific.issn.2542-2987.2019.4.E.1.18-37>
17. Nasqui, S., Curay, E., & Trelles, H. La actitud docente frente a los estudiantes de Educación Inicial con Inclusión Educativa. Yachana Revista Científica. 2018. 7(3): 56-69. <https://doi.org/10.1234/ych.v7i3.552>
18. Arias, Y. Actitudes de los docentes de una institución Educativa privada de Santiago de Surco hacia la persona con discapacidad. Lima: UMC.; 2018.
19. Suárez, M. Actitud docente y la evaluación de la inclusión educativa en instituciones educativas públicas del distrito de Chaclacayo. Perú: Universidad César Vallejo; 2018.
20. Toapanta, J. Actitud del docente frente a la inclusión educativa. Ecuador: Universidad Técnica de Cotopaxi; 2017.
21. Muñoz, P., Velásquez, H., & Asprilla, W. Actitudes docentes frente a la educación para la diversidad. Colombia: Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana; 2018.
22. Yanac, E. Actitud hacia la educación inclusiva en docentes de cuatro instituciones educativas inclusivas de Ventanilla. Perú: Universidad San Ignacio de Loyola; 2019.
23. Mora, P. Actitudes y prácticas pedagógicas inclusivas. Colombia: Universidad Pedagógica Nacional; 2019.
24. Plancarte, P. Índice de Inclusión. Desarrollando el aprendizaje y la participación en las escuelas. Validación de constructo para México. España: Universidad de Valencia; 2016.
25. González, Y., & Triana, D. Actitudes de los docentes frente a la inclusión de estudiantes con necesidades educativas especiales. Educación y Educadores. 2018. 21(2):200-218. <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=83460719002>
26. Sota, B. Actitud de los docentes frente a la inclusión: estudio de caso. Perú: Universidad César Vallejo; 2018.
27. Tello, E. Actitud docente frente a la inclusión educativa de estudiantes con discapacidad en el aprendizaje en aulas regulares del nivel primario. Perú: Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú; 2018.